

LEGAL BASIS OF JOINT COOPERATION OF STATES AGAINST CYBERCRIMES

BAZA LEGALĂ A COOPERĂRII STATELOR ÎMPOTRIVA CRIMELOR CIBERNETICE

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Summary

The socially dangerous consequences of cybercrime committed in a borderless electronic information environment, as well as the regular targeting of individuals and legal entities, transnational corporations, as well as states by organized criminal groups, have become a matter of great concern to the world community.

Gaps in the application of cybercrime prevention measures, as well as shortcomings in their investigation, make it difficult to assess these crimes in a timely manner and increase their transnational nature.

The ineffectiveness of the individual's fight against cybercrime alone makes it necessary to pay special attention to the coordinated activities of law enforcement agencies and government agencies responsible for the security of other electronic information systems by strengthening joint cooperation efforts.

Keywords: *transnational crime, cybercrime, computer information, cyber environment, transnational cooperation*

Both the lack of a single codified legal act on cybercrime by all actors of the international community, as well as the very mixed unification of this institution in domestic legislation, continue to negatively affect the organization of joint measures to combat cybercrime. The peculiarities of cybercrime as a transnational crime («borderlessness», etc.), as well as the ineffectiveness of the fight against these crimes by states alone, have led the international community to prefer only joint cooperation [5, 70].

Today, the revolutionary development of technology is leading to an increase in the types of cybercrime and the diversification and expansion of its classification. In this case, the regular globalization of information processes related to technological innovations provides a comprehensive solution to existing complex problems [14, 106].

Measures to combat cybercrime in international law are mainly defined at two levels: organizational mechanisms and multilateral or bilateral agreements.

Organizational mechanisms play an important role in shaping the legal, technical and other framework for combating cybercrime within complex activities. Leading international organizations can serve as an example of these mechanis-

ms. The United Nations, the G-8 High-Tech Crimes Sub-Group, the Council of Europe, the Commonwealth of Independent States, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations and others are important in drafting important projects, decisions and conventions in the fight against cybercrime. make contributions. Bilateral or multilateral agreements at the intergovernmental, intergovernmental and inter-agency levels also serve as an important tool for building cooperation in the fight against cybercrime.

For the first time in the history of the United Nations, the fight against cybercrime was put on the agenda in 1985 with the participation of member states. Thus, the «Milan Action Plan» announced after the UN Conference on «Crime Prevention and Rehabilitation of Criminals» takes into account the issue of cybercrime and their public safety [6, 87]. Nine years later, in 1994, the United Nations Guide to the Prevention and Control of Computer-Related Crimes contained a definition of computer-related crime, as well as recommendations for the need for international cooperation in this area. In connection with the rapid development of information technology and its regular transmission to the life and activity of society, on December 4, 2000, the General Assembly adopted a Resolution on Combating Criminal Abuse of Information Technology. The resolution (A/res/55/63) stated that «(a) States should eliminate legal loopholes in their legislation and legal practices against those who use information technology to commit crimes, as well as (d) the confidentiality of information and computer systems in legal systems;» they must prevent the abuse of impunity by those who commit illegal acts against its integrity and existence [15, 13]. Then, at the 12th UN Congress on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice (El Salvador Declaration) held in 2010 in El Salvador, Brazil, the General Assembly called on member states to adopt national legislation, best practices, technical assistance and Noting the importance of cooperating for comprehensive assistance, including the exchange of information, he recommended mutual exchange, especially in the private sector [21].

On May 23, 2020, the UN Security Council held its second informal meeting on cyber security to focus on cyber-attacks in order to maintain and safeguard international peace. During the meeting, UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres stressed the global social threat of cybercrime, noting that new technologies are widely used to violate human rights, especially during the COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic, which has become a threat to all humanity [23] .

The G8 is a body set up to discuss important domestic and international economic and political issues, including the heads of state or government of the United States, Japan, Germany, Britain, France, Italy, Canada and Russia. It also establishes working groups and cooperation structures on specific issues, such as transnational organized crime. One of these structures is the G-8 Sub-Group on High-Tech Crimes, established in December 1997. This subgroup, representing the political structures of the eight major countries in the fight against cybercrime, has created a “Cybercrime Network” that operates seven days a week, twenty-four ho-

urs a day. Today, more than 70 countries are involved in this network. The network is primarily concerned with “protecting digital evidence through legal channels [13, 1]. The protection of digital evidence is a very important procedural issue in itself, allowing the states involved in the network to address the procedural shortcomings that arise during the investigation of cybercrime in a more effective way.

The activity of the International Criminal Police Office (INTERPOL) as a coordinated body in the fight against the cybercrime threat should be noted. Interpol’s fight against cybercrime dates back to the late 1970s. Thus, in the presentation of “computer fraud” demonstrated at the Third International Symposium on Fraud held by Interpol on December 11-13, 1979, it was noted that telephones, various means of communication, etc. were used between different countries. Due to the ever-increasing number of communications, computer crimes have become, in essence, international in nature [18, 2]. Thus, for the first time in the history of transnational criminal law, cybercrime went beyond national criminal law under the name of “computer crimes” and became an international crime in the second half of the twentieth century and a term recommended for national criminal law. The fight against cybercrime by Interpol in modern times should be especially appreciated. It works closely not only with member states, but also with the private sector and national Computer Ambulance Commands (CERTs) to facilitate the centralized management of cybercrime investigations and operations.

On September 28, 2021, Interpol organized a global law enforcement cooperation between the French National Gendarmerie, the National Police of Ukraine and the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) and the European Police Organization (Europol), which raised up to 70 million euros. An example of this is the arrest of two suspects in a series of cyber attacks in Ukraine [22].

Among the important legal acts in the international legal fight against cybercrime is the Council of Europe’s Budapest Convention on Cybercrime of 23 November 2001 (with Additional Protocols). The Convention divides cybercrime into five main categories and recommends that member states establish it in their legislation as follows:

- Illegal access to computer data and the confidentiality, integrity and accessibility of the system, illegal seizure, data interference, system interference, etc;
- Cybercrime related to the use of computers, ie as a means of committing computer crimes, especially as a means of manipulating electronic information - this group mainly includes computer fraud and computer fraud;
- Content crimes, ie cybercrimes related to the content of data on a computer network. It should be noted that this group of crimes is more dangerous than others due to the degree of public danger. Thus, crimes related to child pornography, which is given special importance by all countries, and pornographic materials spread on the Internet in general, belong to this group;
- Crimes related to copyright and related rights infringement in the network - infringement of intellectual property rights is at the forefront here. This is be-

cause there are widespread violations of copyright and related rights in modern international law, as well as in national legislation, especially on the Internet, as well as the illegal uploading and distribution of images, music and other files and information on external storage devices;

Acts of racism and xenophobia, which are spread and committed through various computer networks - these crimes, called “new generation crimes”, are also reflected in the Additional Protocol to the European Convention on Cybercrime [20].

As can be seen, the Budapest Convention has grouped cybercrimes, which have a very broad scientific classification, and offered this definition to member states.

Speaking of international institutions, we should also mention the European Union, which is a supranational body. The Annex to the Directive 40/ab of the European Parliament and the Council of Europe of 12 August 2013 on Attacks on Information Systems sets out the minimum rules for the scope of major offenses and sanctions in the field of attacks on information systems. The Directive also aims to facilitate the prevention of such offenses and to develop co-operation between the judiciary and other competent authorities. The directive mainly identifies the following cybercrimes and provides brief explanations about them:

- Illegal access to information systems;
- Illegal system interference;
- Illegal information interference [9].

In the history of the European Union, the establishment in 2013 of a separate body specializing in cybercrime – the European Cybercrime Center - was a very important event for the European space. With the creation of this body, which forms the basis of its activities under Europol, a new classification of cybercrime was formed. Thus, the organization focuses on the fight against the following crimes: cyber-dependent crime - cyber attacks, online child sexual exploitation and online payment fraud [24].

It should be noted that both the online sexual exploitation of children classified as crimes by the European Cybercrime Center and child pornography under Article 9 of the Council of Europe Convention are considered cybercrime at the EU level [11, 19]. Involvement of minors in prostitution or immorality and trafficking in child pornography is not considered a cybercrime, but is reflected in Chapter 22 of the Criminal Code, “Crimes against minors and family relations” [1, 144]. We think that the provision of these crimes in Chapter 22 of the Criminal Code should be considered successful. The fact that these crimes were committed by special cyber methods does not mean that these crimes are considered “cybercrime”. However, if the commission of these crimes using information technology is identified in the dispositions of those crimes as an independent method of committing them, it may be considered expedient.

The international fight against cybercrime is one of the priority issues in the cooperation of the member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States. An example of this is the agreement between the CIS member states on “Cooperation in

the fight against crime in the field of information technology” signed on September 28, 2018 in Dushanbe. According to the agreement, the competent authorities of the member states must be in regular exchange in order to detect and prevent cybercrime. At its meeting on June 23, 2021, the Federation Council ratified the agreement [12].

It should also be noted that Chapter XII of the Model Criminal Code of the CIS member states, adopted on February 17, 1996, is dedicated to “Crimes against information security” and identifies seven types of cybercrime [8]. We would like to remind you that Articles 272-274 of Chapter 28 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation are dedicated to cybercrime [10, 646-647].

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations is another organization that coordinates the joint cooperation of states in the fight against cybercrime. Although the member countries of the Association signed a regional agreement on mutual legal assistance in criminal matters in 2004, the agreement provides for the exchange of information, collection, transmission of electronic evidence, etc. for the investigation of cybercrime. The absence of such provisions did not create the necessary basis for joint action of member states in this area [19].

In this case, the member states signed a special Declaration on “Prevention and Combating Cybercrime” on November 13, 2017 in Manila. The Declaration aims to strengthen the commitments of the member states of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations on the prevention of cybercrime and the level of regional struggle [17, 31].

The League of Arab States is also one of the initiators of joint cooperation in the fight against cybercrime. Thus, the League’s Arab Convention against Information Technology Crimes, adopted in Cairo on December 21, 2010, calls on Arab countries to “fight information technology crimes that threaten their security, interests and the security of their communities and to adopt a general criminal policy aimed at protecting against crimes.”. The Arab Convention was signed by 18 Arab countries, including all six members of the Gulf Cooperation Council [16, 11].

On the other hand, in addition to international and regional agreements in the field of cybercrime, we must emphasize the importance of intergovernmental and interdepartmental agreements. Thus, the Agreement on Cooperation between the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Tajikistan dated August 13, 2007 is dedicated to mutual cooperation in this area at the level of law enforcement agencies, including activities related to cyber security [3]. At the same time, the “Shusha Declaration on Allied Relations between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Turkey” adopted on June 15, 2021 agreed to further develop cooperation in the field of cyber security and promote the importance of joint research, training and mutual technical cooperation. The need to do so was emphasized [2, 4].

The ever-expanding nature of cybercrime also affects the motives of criminals. It is true that according to many authors, the commission of cybercrime sho-

uld be based on motives, not on purpose, because the commission of cybercrimes is based on individual intentions, not on purpose [4, 547]. However, in any case, we think that every element of the subjective aspect expands the scope of the damage and harm of these crimes.

In order to fight transnational cybercrime at a higher international level, it is especially important for states to adopt a common criminal and punitive policy against these crimes. This is because the risk of cyber threats to cyber users, no matter where they are in the world, forces states to strengthen their cooperation for information security and to unite their efforts in a more organized way for a more secure electronic information environment. In the national approach, according to Professor Sh.T.Samadova, crimes that directly violate information security are considered computer crimes in the narrow sense, and at the same time, information security should be understood as the protection of the information sphere of the individual, society and the state [7, 412].

One of the factors that will strengthen cooperation at the international, regional and interstate levels will be the establishment of a single list of specific types of crimes committed in the ever-evolving cyber space and the definition of each of these components in the national criminal legislation of states.

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